

From Individual Development to Organizational Success: The Role of Mentoring Programs

44

Research Article

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Meri Taksi Deveciyan^{a*}, Burçin Ataseven Doğru^b, Osman Özkara^c

^a*Istanbul Kültür University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, International Trade and Finance, Istanbul, Türkiye*

^b*Istanbul Kültür University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Business Administration, Istanbul Türkiye*

^c*New York University*

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to thoroughly examine the effects of the “Give a Hand” mentoring program on individual development and their contribution to organizational success. The program was designed to assess how participants progressed in personal satisfaction, psychological and emotional development, communication skills, and social competencies. The research employed qualitative methods, a phenomenological approach, and semi-structured interviews were conducted with 36 mentors (from the USA, Turkey, and Canada) in the “Give a Hand” mentoring program. The data obtained were analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings demonstrate that mentoring processes play a significant role in enhancing leadership competencies and strengthening participants’ commitment to achieving organizational goals. The study’s findings provide evidence on how mentoring practices can be used as a functional tool on the path from individual development to organizational success. In conclusion, it is demonstrated that mentoring programs should be systematically addressed, and that adopting approaches tailored to participants’ needs will enhance success at both individual and organizational levels. In this context, mentoring practices are expected to contribute to the literature on the sustainable success of organizations as well as providing an opportunity for individuals to improve themselves.

Keywords: Leadership Development, Mentoring Programs, Strategy, Individual Development, Organizational Success

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* Correspondence Author, m.taksideveciyan@iku.edu.tr

INTRODUCTION

Mentoring programs have been used for many years as a critical tool in the process of developing individuals' professional skills, increasing their self-awareness, and determining their career goals (Rekha & Ganesh, 2012). In the context of youth, mentoring is seen as an important tool for boosting young people's self-confidence, helping them establish positive relationships, and reducing risky behaviors. Furthermore, mentoring programs are reported to play a critical role in improving their quality of life by addressing their developmental needs. It is also emphasized that mentoring relationships, if long-term and sustainable, can have lasting and meaningful impacts on the lives of these young people (DuBois et al., 2011). Furthermore, mentoring programs allow young people to expand their social networks by interacting with role models (Britner et al., 2006). DuBois et al. (2002) emphasize that this impact becomes more pronounced when well-designed mentoring programs are implemented effectively and strong mentor-youth relationships are established. Conversely, it is also stated that disadvantaged or at-risk youth benefit most from mentoring programs. It is also warned that programs involving inadequate mentors can be detrimental to young people. Similarly, Britner et al. (2006) stated that the success of mentoring programs depends on the quality of mentor-mentee relationships and their suitability to the needs of the participants. These programs, which also support employees' individual development and increase their job satisfaction and motivation levels, create significant effects on organizational performance (Mittal & Upamanyu, 2017). The contributions of mentoring programs to organizational success, especially in achieving strategic goals, are increasingly attracting attention.

This article examines the multifaceted effects of mentoring programs, from individual development to leadership competencies and ultimately to organizational success, based on the experiences and opinions of mentors who participated in the mentoring program called "Give a Hand". In light of the qualitative data provided by the program participants,

how mentoring processes develop leadership potential and the role of this process in achieving organizational goals are analyzed. Thus, it is aimed to provide an evidence-based framework for the design and implementation of mentoring programs focused on leadership development. The study will be shaped within the framework of the main question of "How do mentoring programs affect the personal development of individuals and the contribution of this development to organizational success?"

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Mentoring can be defined as a relationship between two individuals focused on professional development and learning (Allen & Eby, 2008). The origin of the concept of mentoring is based on Homer's *Odyssey*, where Mentor is depicted as the wise and trusted companion of Odysseus and takes care of his son Telemachus during Odysseus' long journey (Bracken & Davis, 1989). This character gained more importance in Fénelon's *Les Aventures de Télémaque* in 1699 and began to be used in French and English to mean "an experienced and trusted guide". The Oxford English Dictionary states that the term Mentor was first recorded in this sense in 1750, while the widespread use of the concept of mentoring increased significantly in the 20th century (Siskin & Davis, 2000).

This mythological figure has gained a broader meaning over time, defining a relationship in which individuals seek guidance from more experienced and wise people. Mentoring is generally defined as a process in which a mentor (usually an older and more experienced individual) guides a younger or less experienced person in their personal and professional development. This relationship includes not only the transfer of knowledge, but also individual development, career planning, and the development of social skills. In academic and professional contexts, the mentoring process has an important place as a development strategy aimed at maximizing the potential of the learner (Andrews & Wallis, 1999). Mentoring is essentially shaped around two functions: instrumental support and psychosocial support. Instrumental support refers to the mentors providing strategic

guidance to help mentees achieve their career goals.

The type of support includes providing feedback and suggestions to mentees in line with their work goals, as well as creating opportunities to facilitate their career development. Mentors make concrete contributions to their mentees' career journeys by 'sponsoring' them, increasing their visibility, and assigning challenging work tasks. On the other hand, psychosocial support includes mentoring activities aimed at developing mentees' emotional resilience and social competence (Johnson et al., 2007). Mentors provide social support to mentees by showing empathy, understanding their needs through active listening, and encouraging their success. This type of support strengthens mentees' ability to cope with difficulties in work life, while also serving to increase their individual self-confidence. The combination of these two functions makes the mentoring process a multidimensional and effective development tool (Grocutt et al., 2022). In the context of mentors with different cultural backgrounds, mentors can introduce various leadership styles to their mentees and offer them a broader perspective. This diversity plays an important role in the development of strong leadership qualities (Johnson, 2017). Successful leaders must have effective communication skills. Communication is one of the fundamental building blocks of leadership; developing these skills within the mentor-mentee relationship increases leadership impact/development. Mentors try to strengthen their mentees' ability to communicate, listen, and give feedback (DeWaard & Chavhan, 2020). Zhou (2021) emphasizes the importance of communication skills in the dimension of intercultural mentoring. In this context, it is stated that active listening and open communication are critical in overcoming cultural differences in mentoring relationships, establishing mutual understanding, and valuing cultural differences. It is also stated that a good mentor should have the skills of active listening, asking questions, and finding common ground in intercultural mentoring (Zhou, 2021). Jyoti & Sharma (2015) states that "mentoring is a valuable resource for learning and coping with major organizational

changes" (Jyoti & Sharma, 2015) and is a person who adds value to everyone in the mentoring relationship. Mentors aim to improve mentees' decision-making skills by providing advice, analysis, and feedback. In this way, mentees' competence levels increase, which helps their career development. Orpen (1997) states that a good mentor-mentee relationship increases mentees' commitment to the organization. The two main reasons for this are that mentees' commitment to the organization is strengthened because they are respected and loved, and that good relationships make other aspects of the organization more attractive. It is also emphasized that these relationships increase mentees' work motivation, which can positively affect job performance. Aquino et al. (2022) discusses that mentoring increases collaboration in virtual teamwork with effective communication, value sharing, and role sharing. Mentors can increase productivity by recognizing the strengths of team members and creating trust and commitment. In addition, appreciating individuals' contributions encourages their motivation and innovation. In addition, the article states that value sharing is directly related to ethics and transparency. Ethical behavior and transparent communication build trust among team members, while sharing common values strengthens cooperation. In this context, mentors' encouragement of ethical standards and creation of a transparent environment positively affects the success of the team. The "Give a Hand" mentoring program, which constitutes the target audience for this study, is an international non-governmental organization founded in 2015 at The Hill School and aims to support children whose lives have been disrupted by war, migration, and natural disasters. The program creates a transformative experience by providing emotional and academic guidance to refugee and disaster-affected children, connecting them with online volunteer mentors. Since 2019, it has been offering weekly one-hour Zoom meetings, as well as one-on-one online mentoring sessions for children ages 7-13, which include homework assistance, Turkish and English language practice, educational games, and socio-emotional support. As of

today, there are more than 70 active mentor-mentee pairings. Research shows that mentoring during childhood and adolescence not only enhances academic outcomes but also strengthens self-esteem, social skills, and a sense of belonging about the future (Rhodes, 2005; Spencer et al., 2010). For children who have experienced displacement, war, or natural disasters, having a consistent and trusted adult figure is considered a critical factor in promoting psychosocial adjustment. Therefore, programs such as Give a Hand are supported in the literature not only as a form of volunteerism but also as a structured response to the developmental needs of vulnerable children. Because this research examines the Give a Hand program in its specific context. The structure of the program (volunteer mentors, refugee/disaster-affected children, weekly online meetings) is treated as a single social initiative case, and the experiences obtained within this framework are analyzed through qualitative methods. Thus, the study combines elements of a case study design with thematic/phenomenological analysis

Mentoring at the Individual Dimension

Mentoring provided at the individual level helps the individual to develop both technical and social skills, allowing them to take more conscious steps in their career. In addition, this process provides a strong support system that can help the individual achieve their goals and allows them to better manage the uncertainties they may encounter in the business world. Mentoring at the individual level not only increases the person's current knowledge and skills, but also helps them develop the self-confidence and strategic thinking skills that will enable them to be successful in their career in the long term. This type of mentoring provides personalized guidance, allowing the individual to highlight their strengths and improve their weaknesses (Hetty van Emmerik, 2008). At the same time, it can contribute to long-term career planning in the organization by increasing employees' job satisfaction and commitment. Studies also show that when employees receive career mentoring support, their promotability and desire to stay in the organization increase (Van et al., 2018). Mentoring can be seen

as a development process that lasts for the individual's entire life, not just at a certain career stage. Mentoring relationships can help individuals manage transition processes more effectively in different life scenarios (Johnson et.al, 1999). In this way, new career models based on specialization in many areas based on knowledge, skills and talent (flexible career, unlimited career, network-type career and double-step career) have emerged. These changes have also led to the formation of mentoring processes at the individual level, and mentoring relationships have now begun to be customized with the function of providing multi-faceted career development and psychological support (Ceylan, 2004). Mentoring at the individual level is directly related to the characteristics of the protégés in particular. Many studies have shown that the individual characteristics of the protégés have a significant impact on the processes of receiving and providing mentoring in organizational settings. In this context, the transformational leadership of the mentor establishes the strongest positive relationship with both career and psychosocial mentoring support, while the proactiveness of the protégé makes a big difference in receiving career support. Proactive protégés are more likely to receive mentoring support, and this characteristic significantly increases their career development and overall job satisfaction (Ghosh, 2014). While mentoring offers great opportunities for individual development, establishing and maintaining an effective mentor-mentee relationship can also bring various challenges. However, when this process is managed correctly, long-term personal and professional gains are provided for both the mentor and the mentee (Hill et.al, 2022).

Mentoring in the Organizational Dimension

Mentoring is recognized as a significant tool for training and development that supports professional advancement within organizations (Levinson et al., 1978). As a method of training and development, mentoring is not a novel concept. For centuries, these wise men, referred to as mentors, have given advice to young people. Most corporate leaders have had mentors who were vital to their success (Jennings, 1971).

Heidrick and Struggles, Inc. Roche's (1979) report shows that approximately two-thirds of senior executives have mentors and that these executives receive higher salaries, bonuses and total compensation than executives without mentors. It is agreed that a mentor is necessary for young business people to achieve success (Hunt & Michael, 1983). Mentoring also stands out as one of the innovative functions of today's competency-based human resources management. Especially in the last 15 years, technological advances, the spread of information applications and the increase in the qualified workforce have led to radical changes in the business world. This process has also brought about the reshaping of managerial roles and responsibilities due to the increasing knowledge and expectations of employees and the increasing competition. Depending on the purposes it serves, mentoring is defined and applied in different disciplines such as social psychology, management, education and human resources development (Camveren & Vatan, 2018). In an organization, managers abandoning the "command and control" approach and adopting roles such as "development, coaching and mentoring" that focus on supporting the individual development of employees contribute significantly to both the potential of employees and the long-term success of the organization. Human Resources Managers should undertake a strategic role in order to support leadership development throughout the organization, to establish the foundations of coaching and mentoring relationships and to spread these practices, and they should ensure that these processes are implemented effectively and sustainably. While modern organizational structures move away from hierarchical approaches and emphasize the concepts of leadership and teamwork, traditional "manager" titles are increasingly being replaced by more dynamic and functional concepts such as "leader," "mentor" and "coach" that are independent of hierarchical foundations (Çınar, 2007). In this context, many companies have implemented formal mentoring programs and are working to provide benefits for both parties in various ways that have been frequently discussed before. Because mentoring relationships not

only contribute to the career development of individuals, but also affect the general management processes of the organization. In addition, transferring corporate culture and providing a "mechanism for deeper organizational insight top management are some of the benefits that can be listed (Wilson et al., 2017). Again, as evidence that mentoring is increasingly used to adapt to changing work dynamics in the business world, it can be shown that it stands out as an important tool that helps individuals and organizations adapt in processes such as more participatory working arrangements, corporate restructuring, and global expansion (Eby & Lillian, 1997). According to Allen et.al, (2009), it is stated that mentoring programs implemented at the organizational level also directly contribute to general organizational performance. Studies show that employee satisfaction, organizational citizenship behaviors, and learning culture are higher in organizations where mentoring practices are widespread. These findings also show that investing in mentoring programs by organizations can provide a competitive advantage in the long term. As a result, "Mentoring practices have become a strategic tool that helps organizations adapt to the changing business world, beyond being a process that only supports individual development. In the future, mentoring models are expected to gain flexibility and become more adaptable to different organizational and cultural contexts" (Mullen et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

In the study, the phenomenological approach, one of the qualitative research methods, was used to examine the effects of mentoring programs on individuals' personal development and organizational success. The phenomenological approach is defined as a research approach that focuses on examining experiences in depth and understanding the essence of these experiences (Norlyk & Harder, 2010). This design aimed to understand the subjective perspectives of the participants regarding their mentoring experiences. In this context, the semi-structured interview technique was used to obtain in-depth data.

The universe of the study consists of mentors

who participate in mentoring programs. The sample was selected with the purposive sampling method. This method focused on determining the participants who had mentoring experience and could provide the best answer to the research questions (Yıldız, 2017). A total of 36 mentors participated in the study. The participants were young people between the ages of 16-24 who had not yet had their first work experience and who live in Turkey (13 people), America (17 people) and Canada (6 people). The reason why the participants were chosen from among the young people who mentored the children in the "Give a Hand" social responsibility project is that it makes it possible to observe the effects of the mentoring process on individual development in its purest form. These young people, who will be in a working environment for the first time, have the potential to both develop their own competencies and demonstrate the reflections of this experience on organizational success through the mentoring experience. Although the young people who were mentored did not have any previous work experience, the fact that they had taken courses on organizational structure, social impact, and leadership skills during their high school and university education gave them institutional awareness and a sense of responsibility during this volunteer process. At the same time, the fact that the young participants had not yet developed professional habits or specific work patterns allows the development and change effects provided by the mentoring process to be evaluated in a way that is free from external factors. In addition, since these participants do not yet have a pre-formed perception of organizational structure and work processes, they can more easily internalize the knowledge, skills, and leadership characteristics provided by the mentoring process. This allows for a clearer measurement of individual development processes. As a result, this sample group provides an ideal basis for understanding how mentoring programs can create value at the organizational level, as well as their effects on leadership development, sense of belonging, and work commitment. The research data were collected using a semi-structured interview form. The interviews were

conducted via the online Zoom platform; each interview lasted an average of 25-30 minutes. With the permission of the participants, the interviews were recorded and then transcribed and transcribed.

For the validity of the research, participant verification (member-checking) was applied during the data collection process. In this context, interview transcripts were sent to the participants and their comments were checked for accuracy. For reliability, coding was done by two researchers and an inter-coder agreement analysis was performed. The coder agreement was determined as 85% and this rate was considered to support the reliability of the research.

The collected data was examined with thematic analysis, one of the qualitative data analysis methods. First, the interview notes were read carefully and meaningful codes were derived from the data. Then, these codes were brought together and themes were created.

Research Question

Main Problem of the Research

"What is the effect of mentoring programs on the personal development of individuals and the contribution of this development to organizational success?"

Sub-questions

1. What kind of change/development did you feel in yourself after mentoring?
2. How do you expect/think your participation in the mentoring program will be reflected in organizational life?

FINDINGS

The data obtained as a result of the interviews conducted with the mentors are gathered under the following two main themes: Leadership development and Work belonging-Commitment. The sub-themes of these two main themes and the responses from the interviewees regarding the related themes are given below.

Table 1. Theme and Subthemes

Main Theme	Leadership development	Business Loyalty and Commitment
Subthemes	-Communication Skills	-Teamwork and Collaboration
	Active listening	Common Goals
	Open communication	Role Sharing
	-Decision Making Ability	- Alignment with Values
	Situational Analysis	Sharing Values
		Ethics and Transparency

Responses Received from Interviewees Regarding the Communication Skills Sub-Theme of the Leadership Development Main Theme

The responses given by the interviewees regarding the Communication Skills Sub-Theme are summarized as “active listening” and “open communication”, through their own direct expressions, “in vivo” codes, as follows.

“During mentoring, I improved my ability to listen to, guide and perhaps influence children by paying attention to what they say. This significantly increased the communication between us”. G2 (active listening)

“I became more open in sharing my experiences; this allowed both me and the mentees to express ourselves better, I saw myself as a Pioneer”. G5(open communication)

Responses Received from Interviewees Regarding the Communication Skills Sub-Theme of the Decision-Making Ability Main Theme

The responses given by the interviewees regarding the Decision-Making Ability Sub-Theme are summarized as “situational analysis”, through their own direct expressions, “in vivo” codes, as follows.

“In different situations I encountered during the mentoring process, I tried to find the most appropriate solution by analyzing the difficulties experienced. This analysis ability helped me make more conscious decisions, I felt like I gained vision”. G12 (situational analysis)

Responses Received from Interviewees Regarding the Teamwork and Collaboration Sub-Theme of the Work Attachment and Commitment Main Theme

The responses given by the interviewees regarding Teamwork and Collaboration were

summarized as “common goals” and “role sharing”, and also through their own direct expressions, “in vivo” codes, as follows.

“In the mentoring program, we were able to work in a more coordinated manner thanks to the common goals we determined with our teammates. Everyone’s contribution was important and this reinforced our spirit of cooperation, I think I can easily do the same in the workplace”. G18 (common goals)

“We took everyone’s strengths into consideration when distributing tasks within the team. In this way, everyone contributed in the area they were best at, and this strengthened our sense of commitment”. G2 (role sharing)

Responses Received from Interviewees Regarding the Sub-Theme “Compliance with Values” of the Main Theme of Business Loyalty and Commitment

The responses given by the interviewees regarding the Compliance with Values are summarized as “sharing values” and “ethics and transparency”, through their own direct expressions, “in vivo” codes, as follows.

“Reminding our Give a Hand values at every meeting made us feel more connected as a team. As we shared our values, we became more willing to achieve our team’s goals”. G21(Sharing values)

“We were as transparent as possible while trying to implement our values, we built trust within the team. The fact that everyone could express their thoughts openly increased our sense of belonging in the mentoring we did and the work we would do in the future, and helped us solve problems faster”. G30 (Ethics and transparency).

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to examine the effects of mentoring practices on individual development and organizational success through the “Give a Hand Mentoring Program”. The findings are parallel to existing studies in the literature and support the positive effects of mentoring programs on the workforce: Allen & Eby (2007) state that mentoring relationships create significant positive effects on employees’ job satisfaction, psychological well-being, and career development. Similarly, in this study, it was observed that the leadership skills and decision-making abilities acquired by the participants through the mentoring processes increased.

Mentoring is defined as a critical tool in the processes of increasing individuals’ self-awareness and determining career goals (Kram & Isabella, 1985). In this context, the study found that the participants’ sense of personal satisfaction increased and their organizational commitment strengthened. This result is also consistent with the results of the Gareis et al., (2007) and Fountain, (2018) studies; this study shows that mentoring experiences increase individuals’ sense of belonging to the organization. The literature also emphasizes the critical role that mentoring programs play not only in the professional development of young people but also in their personal and social development. DuBois et al. (2011) and Britner et al. (2006) note that through mentoring, young people gain self-confidence, expand their social networks, and develop positive behavioral patterns. This finding is consistent with the observed improvements in communication and leadership skills of young mentors who participated in the “Give a Hand” program. In addition, the potential of mentoring programs to be a strategic tool not only for individuals but also for organizations is noteworthy. The effects of mentoring practices on reinforcing organizational culture and ensuring deep perception rules with senior management have also been addressed by Wilson et al. (2017). In this context, our study reveals that mentoring relationships create significant effects not only on individuals but also at the organizational level. On the other

hand, the effects of mentoring programs do not occur in the same way for every individual. In some studies, it has been stated that there are participants who do not benefit from the mentoring process, and it has been particularly mentioned that mentoring restricts creativity (Tolar, 2012). This situation emphasizes the importance of factors such as the quality of the mentoring relationship, the mentor’s competence level, and the individuals’ initial motivations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examines the multifaceted effects of mentoring practices on individual development and organizational success within the framework of the “Give a Hand Mentoring Program”. The findings reveal that mentoring processes have positive effects on participants’ personal satisfaction, psychological and emotional development, communication skills and social competencies. In addition, data based on the experiences of mentors show that mentoring programs play a critical role in achieving organizational goals as well as leadership development. In this context, the following recommendations are made to increase the effectiveness of mentoring programs:

- Approaches customized to the needs of individuals should be adopted in the design of mentoring programs. In this way, development opportunities can be offered to participants for different competency areas.
- The importance of organizational values and ethical principles should be emphasized from the beginning of the program. Encouraging value sharing among participants can strengthen the sense of cooperation and commitment.
- Trainings to be provided to mentors play an important role in increasing the quality of mentoring relationships. Supports to be provided to mentors, especially in leadership skills and communication, can increase the effectiveness of mentoring processes.
- Ongoing research on the effects of mentoring practices will make significant

contributions to the academic literature. Conducting long-term impact analyses on both individual and organizational success will help understand the evolution of mentoring programs.

As a result, mentoring programs have the potential to develop individuals' leadership competencies as well as making significant contributions at the organizational level. Therefore, systematic consideration and continuous development of mentoring practices are expected to have a positive impact on the success of both individuals and organizations. In addition, one of the limitations of the study is that although interviews were conducted with participants from different countries, differences in the context of countries were not examined, and it can be suggested that researchers interested in the field make comparisons between different countries in the future and even investigate differences in the context of gender in mentors.

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